

Application of various theories on ternary system of heptadecane, butanol and dimethyl sulfoxide at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K

Rita Mehra* and Rekha Israni

Department of Applied Chemistry, M. D. S. University, Ajmer-305 009, India

Fax : 91-0145-441176/443376

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Ultrasonic velocity and density of ternary system of heptadecane, butanol and DMSO as a function of composition and temperature have been measured. The experimental values of ultrasonic velocity are compared with various theoretical models predicted on the basis of free-length theory, ideal-mixing relation, Nomoto relation and Flory theory. There exists a good agreement between the experimental values of ultrasonic velocities and those obtained theoretically by using free-length theory and ideal mixing relation.

The study of physicochemical behavior and molecular arrangements has been a subject of sufficient interest. The measurement of sound velocity and various acoustical and thermodynamic parameters derived from it provide a convenient method for studying molecular interactions particularly in liquid mixtures. In recent years, many successful attempts have been made on experimental and theoretical evaluation of ultrasound velocity and its correlation with various thermodynamic parameters using various models¹. Although an attempt has been made to validate various theoretical models for propanol + *n*-hexane, butanol + *n*-hexane, benzene + propanol, benzene + butanol, toluene + *n*-alkanol hexadecane + *n*-butanol, and hexadecane + *n*-hexanol. But it appears to us that no such investigations have been made on the ultrasonic study of binary and ternary systems of higher alkanes (particularly heptadecane), higher alkanols and DMSO to ensure the validity of these theories. Further, there is not much data to check the validity of these theories at different temperatures. Moreover, alcohols are extremely self-associated while DMSO is polar but not self-associated due to absence of proton-donating ability. DMSO and alcohol have a wide range of applicability in chemical and biological reactions and higher alkanes are added to study the change in the free volume of the mixture.

With this background a study of ultrasonic behavior of binary and ternary mixture of heptadecane + butanol + DMSO has been undertaken over the entire composition range of heptadecane at different temperatures in the range 298.15–318.15 K at 10 K interval. In the present communication an attempt has been made to apply free-length theory, Nomoto relation, Flory theory and ideal mixing relation to deduce ultrasonic velocity in heptadecane + butanol + DMSO at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K. A com-

parative study of the theoretical and experimental values of ultrasonic velocity has been made for this system.

Results and Discussion

The theoretical values of ultrasonic velocities have been evaluated using the following relationships.

Flory's statistical theory : Flory's statistical theory has no direct relation with ultrasound velocity. It has been used to calculate ultrasound velocity through Auerbach relation which utilize theoretical values of surface tension as obtained by Flory's statistical theory². The ultrasound velocity is given by the relation,

$$C_m = \left(\frac{\sigma_m}{6.3 \chi 10^{-3} \rho_{mix}} \right)^{2/3} \quad (1)$$

Ideal mixing relation IMR : According to the theory of ideal mixing, ultrasonic velocity in ternary liquid mixture is given by the relation³,

$$\frac{1}{X_1 M_1 + X_2 M_2 + X_3 M_3} \frac{1}{C_m^2} = \frac{X_1}{M_1 C_1^2} + \frac{X_2}{M_2 C_2^2} + \frac{X_3}{M_3 C_3^2} \quad (2)$$

where *X*, *M* and *C* stand for mole-fraction, molecular weight and ultrasound velocity of pure components and subscripts 1, 2 and 3 stand respectively for heptadecane, butanol and DMSO, and *C_m* is the ultrasound velocity of mixture.

Free-length theory (FLT) : Jacobson's free-length theory⁴ is calculated using the formula,

$$u^{FLT} = \frac{K}{L_{mix} \rho_{mix}^{1/2}} \quad (3)$$

where *K* is the Jacobson's constant and it is temperature-dependent constant, *L_{mix}* the intermolecular free-length in mixture and *ρ_{mix}* the density of mixture.

Nomoto relation (NOM) : The empirical formula for sound velocity in binary mixture given by Nomoto⁵ can be written as

$$u^{\text{NOM}} \left(\frac{X_1 R_1 + X_2 R_2 + X_3 R_3}{X_1 V_1 + X_2 V_2 + X_3 V_3} \right)^3 = \left(\frac{R_m}{V_m} \right)^3 \quad (4)$$

where, $R_m = X_1 R_1 + X_2 R_2 + X_3 R_3$

$$V_m = X_1 V_1 + X_2 V_2 + X_3 V_3$$

and X , R and V are mole fractions, molar sound velocity and molar volumes and subscripts 1, 2 and 3 stand respectively for heptadecane, butanol and DMSO.

Table 1. Ultrasonic velocity (m s^{-1}) calculated theoretically and experimentally for ternary mixture of heptadecane (x_1), butanol (x_2) and DMSO (x_3) at different temperatures*

Sl. No.	x_1	x_2	U^{EXP}	U^{FLT}	U^{NOM}	U^{ID}	U^{Flory}
At 298.15 K							
1.	0.0000	0.5127	1340.00	1336.07	1314.02	1339.00	1312.00
2.	0.05678	0.4836	1345.82	1342.97	1324.04	1344.00	1321.97
3.	0.1375	0.4201	1346.00	1347.08	1341.83	1345.94	1338.08
4.	0.2258	0.3969	1349.08	1348.77	1361.84	1348.14	1361.04
5.	0.3597	0.3282	1351.84	1351.04	1345.92	1352.92	1342.22
6.	0.4483	0.3020	1352.74	1351.09	1331.94	1351.82	1332.00
7.	0.5583	0.2264	1352.91	1353.44	1337.07	1353.01	1341.00
8.	0.6986	0.1521	1354.08	1353.94	1334.98	1352.94	1342.97
9.	0.7842	0.1106	1356.99	1354.88	1348.00	1355.89	1331.00
10.	0.8360	0.0565	1357.01	1357.98	1348.72	1356.91	1351.92
11.	1.0000	0.0000	1358.00	1358.00	1358.00	1358.00	1358.00
At 308.15 K							
1.	0.0000	0.5127	1287.33	1284.11	1264.84	1283.24	1263.72
2.	0.05678	0.4836	1289.41	1288.12	1268.12	1287.43	1264.12
3.	0.1375	0.4201	1291.73	1287.42	1269.99	1284.32	1268.19
4.	0.2258	0.3969	1292.84	1290.00	1274.49	1291.43	1273.48
5.	0.3597	0.3282	1297.88	1294.08	1294.08	1296.18	1291.09
6.	0.4483	0.3020	1299.01	1297.94	1291.84	1296.12	1292.77
7.	0.5583	0.2264	1303.33	1299.74	1291.77	1299.14	1294.83
8.	0.6986	0.1521	1306.31	1304.44	1301.11	1306.12	1293.94
9.	0.7842	0.1106	1308.11	1307.12	1301.74	1308.24	1300.04
10.	0.8360	0.0565	1309.24	1308.14	1304.79	1309.12	1301.07
11.	1.0000	0.0000	1312.00	1312.00	1312.00	1312.00	1312.00
At 318.15 K							
1.	0.0000	0.5127	1253.61	1252.41	1231.44	1251.21	1232.12
2.	0.05678	0.4836	1254.12	1234.01	1234.12	1251.11	1238.43
3.	0.1375	0.4201	1256.44	1255.12	1238.44	1255.04	1239.19
4.	0.2258	0.3969	1258.47	1256.12	1239.12	1255.94	1240.73
5.	0.3597	0.3282	1260.11	1259.13	1241.14	1257.48	1242.44
6.	0.4483	0.3020	1261.24	1260.14	1244.18	1261.84	1245.28
7.	0.5583	0.2264	1264.74	1262.78	1246.12	1264.84	1247.84
8.	0.6986	0.1521	1264.91	1262.41	1247.44	1266.81	1249.84
9.	0.7842	0.1106	1265.84	1263.18	1250.12	1262.88	1250.12
10.	0.8360	0.0565	1266.12	1265.44	1251.14	1265.11	1251.74
11.	1.0000	0.0000	1268.00	1268.00	1268.00	1268.00	1268.00

* U^{FLT} = Free length theory, U^{NOM} = Nomoto relation, U^{ID} = ideal mixing relation, U^{Flory} = Flory's theory.

The experimental and theoretical values of ultrasonic velocity are listed in Table 1. The data reveal that ultrasonic velocities computed from FLT and IMR exhibit satisfactory agreement with the experimental values. However, deviation from experimental data has been observed on comparing it with theoretical values obtained by applying Nomoto relation and Flory's theory. It has been reported earlier that the free-length theory and Nomoto relation are not applicable to associated liquids like alcohols, but in present case it has been observed that free-length theory fully agrees with the experimental data, indicating the non-prevalance of any hydrogen bonded association in the system under study.

Heptadecane is a non-polar chain molecule with only van der Waal interactions present in it. The deviation in Nomoto relation may be attributed to the fact that alcohol and DMSO are self-associated liquids, and such associations is hindered due to S=O and O=O interactions which will also be of weak nature in presence of heptadecane.

The average percentage deviation in FLT, NOM, ID and Flory's theory at 298.15 K are 0.22, 0.90, 0.05, 1.2, at 308.15 K are 0.28, 1.03, 0.09, 1.29 and at 318.15 K are 0.38, 1.44, 0.16, 1.32, respectively. The deviation observed in Flory theory is expected because of the difficulties in applying Flory's theory to these systems. All the components of ternary liquid mixtures especially associated liquids do not strictly obey the theorem of corresponding states which has been used as a basis for the deviation of equations and which in turn effect the variation of sound velocity derived from eqn. (1). Further, application of reduced surface tension equation to a mixture by treating it as if it is made up of an equivalent single component is not desirable. Apart from all these there can be deviations in using Auerback relation⁵.

Of the four theories discussed above IMR and FLT are found to be more suitable in predicting the ultrasonic velocities for the system at all temperatures taken for the present investigation, while Flory's theory and Nomoto relation exhibit deviation from experimental values. Thus we conclude that the theories of liquids especially NMR and Flory theory need to be modified in order to account for molecular interactions in associated liquids. Further studies are in progress so as to interpret for the adequacy of the theories to give a comprehensive account of the experimental manifestation.

Experimental

Heptadecane, butanol and DMSO (A.R., purity >99%) were used and their purity was checked by comparing the boiling points and densities with those reported in literature. Procedure adopted for preparation of ternary mixtures was the same as earlier⁶.

Ultrasonic velocity was measured by a single crystal

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ultrasonic interferometer at 2 MHz frequency at different temperatures in a thermostat ($\pm 0.1^\circ$). The accuracy of velocity measurement was $\pm 0.03\%$. The density ($\pm 0.024\%$ error) was determined by a bicapillary pycnometer.

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